

Background

Aging of lithium-ion batteries in electric vehicles (BEVs) is influenced by a complex interplay of factors (e. g., temperature, state of charge, current). Understanding them is critical to mitigate loss of performance and ensure safe and long-lasting battery operation.

Recent studies ((Ali et al. 2023; Che et al. 2023; Schlasza et al. 2014)) highlight solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) growth and lithium plating as dominant aging drivers under typical operating conditions. These mechanisms are highly sensitive to temperature, current rates, and depth of discharge (DOD), making operational conditions a key determinant of degradation (Fig. 1).

In order to capture the impact of real-world usage patterns and operation environments, mathematical models of battery packs and their degradation represent a cost-effective alternative to time-consuming laboratory or field testing. Two fundamental paradigms exist: semi-empirical and physics-based.

While semi-empirical models offer simplicity, they often lump aging effects and lack spatial resolution. Physics-based models, though more complex, provide deeper insight into aging dynamics, which is beneficial to ensure a higher level of safety throughout the lifetime of a battery pack.

All these considered, we propose a low-complexity aging model that integrates temperature and electrochemical states as stress factors into a reduced-order electrochemical framework, for both cyclic and calendaric degradation.

Figure 1. Summary of operational limits and recommendations for commonly used Li-ion cells

Physics-based Aging Model

■ Copper ■ SEI
■ Anode ■ Isolated graphite
■ Separator ■ Plated Li
■ Graphite ● Li-ion

Figure 2. Aging mechanisms and stages of degradation

The aging model presented in this paper focuses on capturing the identified two most critical degradation mechanisms: SEI growth and lithium plating. These mechanisms are known to accelerate under high SOC, low or high temperatures, and aggressive cycling conditions often encountered in real-world EV operation.

The model introduces three aging-related state variables:

- SEI accumulation, c_{SEI}
- Plated lithium, c_{Li}
- Apparent loss of active material (LAM), represented by the time-varying volume fraction ϵ

The aging process is described as follows (Yang et al. 2017):

- The surface of active material particles in the anode react to form an SEI layer,
- When this reaches a critical size, and the electrochemical state favors it, metallic lithium is formed,
- In parallel, isolation of particles is assumed due to (non-modeled) particle cracking and pore clogging, all of which translates into apparent loss of active material (see Fig. 2).

Our model assumes homogeneous SEI growth and lithium plating across the electrode thickness, which simplifies the spatial complexity while retaining physical relevance. Importantly, the SEI growth is driven by the consumption of ethylene carbonate (EC), whose diffusion is temperature-dependent and modeled using an Arrhenius-type expression. To account for calendaric aging, the EC diffusion coefficient is further modified to depend on SOC, capturing the increased degradation observed during high-SOC storage.

Case Study

This case study applies the proposed aging model to predict battery degradation in a mid-size electric vehicle, considering realistic operational and environmental conditions. The simulations are based on a battery pack that uses immersion cooling, where the cells are in direct contact with a thermally conductive fluid (see Fig. 3). To reflect realistic thermal management, the modeled scenario implements a hysteresis-based control strategy and heat transfer conditions:

- Cooling is activated at 30 °C and deactivated at 25 °C.
- Heating is activated at 10 °C and deactivated at 15 °C.
- The system assumes a heat transfer coefficient of 100 W/m²K for immersion cooling (cell to fluid) and 1 W/m²K for passive convection to ambient air.

Figure 3. Immersion cooled battery stack

Two contrasting climates – Seville (hot) and Gothenburg (cold) – were selected to evaluate the impact of ambient temperature. The profile represents a typical WLTC with a duration of approximately 30 min and distance of 23 km. Fig. 4 shows that higher usage and warmer climates accelerate degradation, while Fig. 6 highlights the risk of lithium plating under insufficient heating in cold environments (heater activation temperature at 5 °C, deactivation at 10 °C).

Figure 4. Comparison between the effect of number of cycles per day and ambient temperature

The model also enables detailed analysis of charging strategies. In an overnight charging scenario, the battery is charged at low C-rates on specific days. In contrast, opportunity charging allows recharging whenever the cell voltage drops below 3.6 V. Fig. 5 illustrates how these strategies affect cell voltage and anode potential. As a result, Fig. 7 shows that opportunity charging can extend battery life by over 400 days compared to overnight charging, for the same SOH in the given example.

The results highlight that charging strategy, DOD and thermal management strategy should be chosen as a function of the climatic conditions, usage pattern, etc.

Figure 6. 4xWLTC per day, Gothenburg, lower heating temperature

Figure 5. Cell voltage and anode potential considering night and opportunity charge options (Seville)

Figure 7. Remaining capacity results considering night and opportunity charge options (Seville)

Model Calibration

The model calibration process involved determining the electrochemical, thermal, and aging parameters of a cylindrical 21700 lithium-ion cell (5 Ah capacity) with a high-nickel NMC cathode and graphite anode. Geometric and thermal properties – such as electrode area, particle size, and heat capacity – were measured either in-house or via external labs. Electrochemical parameters like diffusion coefficients and open-circuit voltages were sourced from literature or obtained experimentally. The ohmic resistance was derived from ACIR measurements.

For aging model calibration, both cyclic and calendaric aging tests were conducted internally. Parameters such as the SEI side reaction potential U_{SEI} , EC diffusion coefficient D_{EC} , and activation energy E_a were tuned using experimental data and literature references, most notably (Yang et al. 2017) and (Zhao, Choe, and Kee 2018). The model was validated under various SOC, current, and temperature conditions, showing good agreement with observed capacity fade and lithium plating onset.

Figure 8. Calendaric aging validation results at 50% SOC

Figure 9. Cyclic aging validation results, 1C charge / 1.5C discharge (one cell, blue at 22°C, red at 40°C)

Future Work

Going forward, we aim to enhance the model by incorporating electrolyte concentration dynamics, as well as developing a P2D version with minimal discretization complexity to compare the influence of model inaccuracies. Additionally, experimental tests are currently being conducted to verify the simulated results presented.

Highlights

- Low-complexity physics-based battery aging model capturing SEI growth and lithium plating.
- Hybrid model formulation combining cyclic and calendaric aging with temperature and SOC-dependent behavior.
- Validated against experimental results from various cycling and calendar aging tests under different conditions.
- Enables simulation of real-world scenarios including climatic conditions, driving profiles and operation strategies.

References

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